

Modeling Crack Propagation in Composites using Constitutively Informed Particle Dynamics

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Dr. Venkatesh

Constitutively Informed Particle Dynamics
(CPD) simulations

Prof. G. Li

Prof. M. Uchimali

Dr. Elham Kiyani

Prof. A. Peyvan

Deep Operator Networks
(DeepONets) learning models

Prof. Karniadakis

Modes and complexity of modeling failure in composites

Delamination at the interface between two plies of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite under an impact

Fiber-matrix debonding: section perpendicular to the fiber axis

Motivation

Modes and complexity of modeling failure in composites

Fiber-matrix debonding: section perpendicular to the fiber axis

Modeling Failure

(Addressing material discontinuity)

Continuum

Ex: Phase field method
(Damage parameter Varying from 0 to 1)

Discrete

Particle-based method
(Inherently allows empty spaces & fracture)

Motivation

Modes and complexity of modeling failure in composites

Crack path in the composite specimen modeled with particle based discrete element method for volume fractions (a) 0.1, (b) 0.3, and (c) 0.4.

Literature Survey: State of the Art

Advantages of discrete methods in simulating crack as reported in the literature

- (a) Lattice discrete particle simulation of projectile impact and penetration through fiber-reinforced concrete panels
- (b) Rigid-body-spring simulation of tensile fracture of a concrete cylinder, compared with experimental damage

Limitation of discrete methods in the literature

Type of interaction	Relation between elastic constants (E, ν) and spring constants (k, k_1 , k_2 , k_θ)
Linear springs	$k = \sqrt{3}E, \nu = \frac{1}{3}$
Linear springs with nearest and next nearest interactions	$k_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}E}{8}, k_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}E}{8}, \nu = \frac{1}{3}$
Linear springs with nearest interactions and angular springs	$k = \frac{2\sqrt{3}E}{3(1-\nu)}, k_\theta = \frac{2\sqrt{3}E(1-3\nu)l^2}{9(1-\nu^2)}$ $-1 < \nu \leq \frac{1}{3}$
Linear springs with nearest, next nearest interactions as well as angular springs	$k_2 = mk_1, k_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}E}{3(1-\nu)(1+3m)}$ $k_2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}Em}{3(1-\nu)(1+3m)}, k_\theta = \frac{2\sqrt{3}E(1-3\nu)l^2}{9(1-\nu^2)}, \nu = \frac{1}{3}$
Linear springs along horizontal, vertical direction and angular springs	$k = 2E, k_\theta = \frac{El^2}{2}, \nu = 0$
Linear springs along horizontal, vertical and diagonal direction	$k_1 = \frac{3E}{2}, k_2 = \frac{3E}{8}, \nu = \frac{1}{3}$
Linear springs along horizontal, vertical and diagonal direction as well as angular springs	$k_1 = \frac{2E}{(1+\nu)}, k_2 = \frac{E\nu}{(1-\nu^2)}, k_\theta = \frac{(1-3\nu)El^2}{2(1-\nu^2)}$ $-1 < \nu \leq \frac{1}{3}$

The material properties that can be modeled are often limited by the network architecture and require additional, sometimes unphysical, parameters.

“How can we develop a discrete modeling system that directly incorporates the constitutive matrix of the material?”

Constitutively Informed Particle Dynamics

- Consider the linear transformation $\mathbf{F}_d = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_d(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ for each triangle $\mathcal{T}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{d}_{\beta\alpha} &= \mathbf{F}_d \mathbf{r}_{\beta\alpha}, \\ \mathbf{d}_{\gamma\alpha} &= \mathbf{F}_d \mathbf{r}_{\gamma\alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

- Discrete form of deformation gradient,

$$\mathbf{F}_d = (\mathbf{d}_{\beta\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{d}_{\gamma\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{e}_2) (\mathbf{r}_{\beta\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{r}_{\gamma\alpha} \otimes \mathbf{e}_2)^{-1}$$

- We propose that the energy of the triangle $\mathcal{T}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ can be taken as

$$W_{\alpha\beta\gamma} = V_{\alpha\beta\gamma} \tilde{\psi}(\mathbf{E}_d)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_d = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}_d^T \mathbf{F}_d - \mathbf{1})$ and $\tilde{\psi}$ is the free energy of the material.

For linear elastic materials, $\tilde{\psi} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E}$

- Total energy of discrete model is

$$W = \bar{W}(\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_N; \mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N)$$

- Interaction forces are now given by

$$\mathbf{f}_i = -\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial \mathbf{y}_i}$$

- Equation of motion for each particle

$$m_i \frac{d^2 \mathbf{y}_i}{dt^2} + c \frac{d \mathbf{y}_i}{dt} = -\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial \mathbf{y}_i}$$

where m , and c represents mass and damping, respectively.

Venkatesh Ananchaperumal, Srikanth Vedantam, Mahendaran Uchimali, A discrete particle model study of the effect of temperature and geometry on the pseudoelastic response of shape memory alloys International Journal of Mechanical Sciences (2022)

Constitutively Informed Particle Dynamics with heat diffusion

Thermal Cracks during Quenching

Quenched from 1100 K

Quenched from 1400 K

Venkatesh Ananchaperumal, Srikanth Vedantam, Mahendaran Uchimali,
 Development of coupled thermoelastic discrete model for thermal shock cracking in brittle materials: Parametric analysis of crack patterns
 Materials Science and Engineering: A (2025)

Phase transformation during debonding of the Shape Memory Alloy wire

For thermo elastic materials, $\bar{\psi} = \psi(\mathbf{E}, \theta)$

(S. Vedantam et al. (2005))

- Austenite phase taken as reference configuration ($\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{0}$)
- Martensite is considered as deformed configuration ($\mathbf{E}_{1,2} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{U}_{1,2}^2 - \mathbf{1})$)

(Hongshuai Lei et al., 2012)

Detwinning of twinned martensitic wire during pullout test simulated by CPD method

Venkatesh Ananchaperumal, Srikanth Vedantam,
Modeling the role of phase boundaries on the pullout response of shape memory wire reinforced composites
Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures (2023)

Case Studies: CPD Data For DeepONet Training

Domain and loading condition considered

Case	Parametrization Strategy	Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Number of Samples	Fracture Accounted
Case 1	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	40	No
Case 2	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	50	Yes
Case 3	Varying hole radius	$r = 0.5$ to 1.5	$h = 1.5$	51	Yes

Stress Concentrations Near Domain Discontinuities

Stress concentration studies and validation at the crack tip and around the hole

Stress concentration at crack-tip

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{\sigma_{\infty}}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{a}{x}\right)^2}}$$

Stress concentration at hole

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{\sigma_{\infty}}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^2 \right) + \frac{\sigma_{\infty}}{2} \left(1 + 3 \left(\frac{r}{x}\right)^4 \right)$$

Max. & Min. principal stress direction

Crack Path Interaction With Domain Discontinuity

Influence of domain discontinuities on the crack propagation

Crack path reported in a 2009 article

Geometry and loading condition we used in CPD

y
z_x

Crack path from CPD simulation

Crack Path Interaction With Hole

Influence of domain discontinuities on the crack propagation

NOTE: These animations show the final crack path from various simulation

Case 2: Varying pre-crack notch height (d), keeping constant r

Case 3: Varying the radius of the hole (r) keeping constant h

Crack Path Interaction With Hole

Influence of domain discontinuities on the crack propagation

NOTE: These animations show the final crack path from various simulation

Crack traps at $h < 0.4$

$$h_{trap} = \frac{1 + 0.4}{1} = 1.4$$

Crack traps at $r > 1.1$

$$h_{trap} = \frac{1.5 (const.)}{1.1} = 1.36$$

$$\mathbf{u}(\xi) = \sum_{k=1}^p \tilde{b}_k(\mu) \cdot \tilde{t}_k(\xi)$$

$\tilde{b}_k(\mu)$: Output of the **branch net**
 $\tilde{t}_k(\xi)$: Output of the **trunk net**

$$a_T^{(l)} = S_B^{(l)} \circ \sigma \left(W_T^{(l)} a_T^{(l-1)} + b^{(l)} \right)$$

$S_B^{(l)}$: Cumulative features from earlier branch layers
 \circ : Element-wise multiplication

Performance of DeepONet and Fusion DeepONet

Case	Parametrization Strategy	Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Number of Samples	Fracture Accounted
Case 1	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	40	No
Case 2	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	50	Yes
Case 3	Varying hole radius	$r = 0.5$ to 1.5	$h = 1.5$	51	Yes

- True
- Prediction

$h = 0.05, r = 1$

Performance of DeepONet and Fusion DeepONet

Case	Parametrization Strategy	Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Number of Samples	Fracture Accounted
Case 1	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	40	No
Case 2	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	50	Yes
Case 3	Varying hole radius	$r = 0.5$ to 1.5	$h = 1.5$	51	Yes

- True
- Prediction

$h = 1.8, r = 1$

Performance of DeepONet and Fusion DeepONet

Case	Parametrization Strategy	Radius (cm)	Height (cm)	Number of Samples	Fracture Accounted
Case 1	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	40	No
Case 2	Varying pre-crack notch height	$r = 1$	$h = 0$ to 2	50	Yes
Case 3	Varying hole radius	$r = 0.5$ to 1.5	$h = 1.5$	51	Yes

- True
- Prediction

Comparison of the relative error over time

Use Cases Of This Study

Crack interaction with two holes

Crack interaction with two reinforcements in a composite

Future Collaborative Study

Non-destructive testing and simulations to know the exact location of voids, and micro-cracks

Type of stimulation	Impact damage			Wall thinning			Two through-sample cracks		
	Image	SNR	Apparent lateral size, mm	Image	SNR	Apparent lateral size, mm	Image	SNR	Apparent lateral size, mm
Optical pulsed (Xenon tube)		18	18×28	-	-	-		8	37×19
Optical pulsed (halogen lamps)		43	19×23		27	10×12		59	32×17
Optical thermal wave (halogen lamps)		32	18×14		26	9×8		54	23×11
Ultrasonic IR thermography		350	43×28	-	-	-		38	33×21
Ultrasonic laser vibrometry		23	48×48		21	57×48		22	45×42
Laser ultrasonics		-	63×42		-	13×11	-	-	-

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- AIM for Composites website: www.aimforcomposites.com

U.S. DEPARTMENT
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ArXiv article:
Crack Path Prediction with
Operator Learning using Discrete
Particle System data Generation
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.01976>

